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ENCHYTRAEIDS (ENCHYTRAEIDAE, OLIGOCHAETA) IN MIDFIELD SHELTERBELTS OF DIFFERENT AGE AND IN ADJOINING CROPLANDS

ABSTRACT: The objective of this paper was to recognize the influence of forest strips planted (as the shelterbelts) in agricultural area, on adjoining cereal fields basing on the distribution and composition of enchytraeid community. Species composition, density and individual size of enchytraeids were estimated in October and April 2003–2005 along two transects: 6 and 11 years old shelterbelts > ecotones > fields (at a distance of 15 and 50 m. from the wood strip) and in two reference sites: large (about 100 ha) forest stand and the field (“control” field) located in deforested area. The results have been compared with the published results of the previous studies made in the same area four years before (1999–2000).

Samples were collected with soil corer 10 cm² in area and 15 cm deep. Ten samples in each site were taken twice a year. Sixteen species were found in total. The range of density and biomass of enchytraeids for all study sites accounted for 1.6 to 15.3 ind.m⁻² and 55 to 956 mg f.wt. m⁻² (i.e. 15–308 mg d.w.) respectively. The lowest density was observed in the control field located in the deforested area. However, density and biomass of enchytraeids in the fields accounted for 67% and 47% respectively of those in shelterbelts. Species composition of enchytraeids in the young (2–11 yrs old) forest strips and in the adjacent fields was similar, however different from those in the forest stand and in old (150 yrs) shelterbelt.

The response of enchytraeids to grass litter introduced on the soil surface was assessed in the

experiment performed in a control field and in the transect of wood strip > field. The 7–10 portions of dried grass *Dactylis glomerata* (L.), (10 g each) were exposed in each plot for 12 and 18 months. More animals was found in the upper soil layer taken below the exposed litter as well as the density of all enchytraeids and percent share of the dominant genus *Enchytraeus* increased in the soil after 18 months of litter exposure.

KEY WORDS: enchytraeids, density, species composition, fields, wood strips, litter

1. INTRODUCTION

The studies were carried out in an agricultural landscape where the midfield shelterbelts were planted since the XIX (General D. Chłapowski Landscape Park near Turew, Poznań province, Western Poland). The shelterbelts (woodlots, woodstrips) were planted to diversify the landscape as well as to change physical and chemical conditions in field habitats like the chemistry of ground waters, barriers against wind erosion etc. (Bartoszewicz and Ryszkowski 1996, Ryszkowski 1996). Enchytraeid communities in this area are well recognized. Pioneer studies on this group were carried out in Poznań Province

in 1920th by Moszyński (1932) and the density and productivity of this group were estimated in Turew area between 1975 and 1980 by Kasprzak (1982) and Ryl (1977, 1980). The interdisciplinary studies on the effect of woodlots on litter decomposition rate and on the fauna of surrounding fields were carried out in Turew area in the years 1999–2000 (Kajak *et al.* 2003). It was found that enchytraeids accounted for 2–5% of the total biomass of soil animals of crop fields (Karg and Ryszkowski 1996) and in the absence of earthworms they are the most abundant detritophages, important for soil processes. After 25 years of intensive agricultural management the density and species diversity of enchytraeids remained the same but the individual size of animals decreased due to higher contribution of small size species and smaller size of individuals within the same species. The per cent difference between the density of animals in crop fields and in woodlots was higher for enchytraeids than for the other taxa of soil animals (Nowak 2004).

This paper is a continuation of former studies performed in the years 1999–2000 (Nowak 2004) and was aimed to assess the effect of midfield shelterbelts on enchytraeid communities of adjacent fields. One of the causes of the low density of soil animals in the fields is low input of crop residues. In the studies the response of enchytraeids to the increased input of detritus was checked – in the special experiment *in situ*.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

Studies on densities and species composition of enchytraeids were carried out in Turew area (Poznań province, Western Poland) in autumn (October) and spring (April) between 2003 and 2005, on the same soils (alfisols, slightly loamy sand over light loam, Marcinek 1996) and on the same sites as in 1999–2000 (Nowak 2004). Samples were taken from ten plots. They were collected along two transects across 6 and 11 years old wood strips (S6, S11), their eastern ecotones (E_e) (i.e. the border between the wood strip and the field) and the field itself – 15 m (F_{15}) and 50 m (F_{50}) from the ecotone. Sometimes the last two sites were combined as the one

and marked as F6 and F11 respectively. These sites were studied for the second time, firstly – in 2000 when they were marked as S2, S7, F2, F7 (Nowak 2004). The samples were taken also on two control sites: the field located in a large complex of crop fields without any woods in the vicinity (FC) and the large (100 ha) forest stand (Wo) neighbouring the older shelterbelt S11.

Fields (about 10 ha) were sown alternately by wheat and maize or barley. Woodlots were 15–18 m wide and 350–1600 m long. The strips were planted with 15–18 tree species (among others oak, maple, birch, beech, elm, pine). The forest (Wo) was composed mainly of Scots pine with a large share of common oak (Ryszkowski *et al.* 2003).

At every sampling occasion ten soil samples of an area of 10 cm² and 15 cm deep were taken with a corer. Each sample was divided into 5 cm thick layers and the animals were extracted with the wet method using the O'Connor's funnels. Enchytraeids were measured under binocular to the nearest 0.5 mm which enabled to calculate their individual biomass acc. to the formula of Makulec (1983):

$$y = 6.22 \times \text{Exp}.1.55 \quad (1)$$

$$Y = 20.14 \ln y - 62.38 \quad (2)$$

where: x – length in mm, y – biomass of the animal in μg , Y – dry weight in μg

The experiment *in situ* was performed in order to recognise the effect of additional litter input on soil fauna (details in Szanser 2000, Szanser unpublished). Litter portions (10 g of dried mass of cocksfoot *Dactylis glomerata*, covering an area of 100 cm²) were placed in October 2002 in special containers (PVC rings with drilled holes covered with a nylon gauze of a mesh size of 1 mm) in 11 yrs old shelterbelt – S11, in adjoining field (E_e , F_{15} , F_{50}) and in the control field (FC). After 12 months (on 6th October 2004) and after 18 months (on 18th April 2005). 7–10 soil samples were taken below the exposed litter and in its close surrounding from each site to estimate the density and composition of enchytraeids.

Results were tested with ANOVA, Student t-test and the test “u” for differences with proportion. Euclidean distances and linkage clustering were used in cluster analysis to evaluate similarities of communities between sites.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Enchytraeid communities of fields and shelterbelts

Both studies – present (2003–2005) and previous (1999–2000) ones (Nowak 2004) were performed in the years unfavourable for soil fauna due to very low precipitation (Fig. 1). From the autumn 1999 to the spring of 2004 precipitation was up to 28% lower than the long term mean value. Only during two six months periods, October to May in 1999 and 2005 the precipitation significantly exceeded long term mean value (Ryszkowski *et al.* 2003). First assessment of en-

chytraeid abundance made in October 2003 after more than 4 years drought period were close to zero. Not earlier than in April 2004 animals' density reached the values comparable with those noted in the year 2000. Basing on precipitation records it was assumed that density and biomass of enchytraeids obtained in the "average" year 2004 should be taken as representative value.

The enchytraeids' numbers were found to be equally variable in the field than in the shelterbelt, except in 2000 (Fig.1). Spatial variation measured as the ratio of standard deviation to mean (for all data) density (CV%) showed that the differences between sites were insignificant. The respective values

Table 1. Comparison of enchytraeids' density and biomass in shelterbelts and adjacent fields
Sites: S2, S5, S7, S11 and S150 – the shelterbelts of different age (number of years after planting follows the letter), Wo – control forest stand, F2, F6, F7, F11 and F150 – the fields accompanying the respective shelterbelt, F0 and FC – control fields located in the deforested area.
For F0, F2, F7, F150 and S2, S5, S7, S150 – the data from 2000 are presented according to Nowak (2004), for other sites – data for 2004 from the present study (in bold).

Sites	Density 10 ³ m ⁻² ±SE		Individual size mm±SE		Biomass mg f.w. m ⁻²
Fields:					
F0	4.1	1.2	2.95	0.13	137
FC	3.3	1.6	2.25	0.21	72
F2	4.9	1.0	2.70	0.11	142
F6	8.2	0.6	2.61	0.08	226
F7	3.4	0.6	3.18	0.12	127
F11	8.8	1.6	2.94	0.14	291
F150	13.2	4.3	2.76	0.13	394
mean	6.6	1.5 *	2.77	0.12 *	196
Wood sites:					
S2	6.9	1.5	2.87	0.09	220
S5	12.7	1.6	4.92	0.19	956
S6	11.5	3.5	3.02	0.20	397
S7	15.3	2.7	4.10	0.16	848
S11	1.6	0.3	3.03	0.28	55
S150	11.9	2.5	3.26	0.14	466
Wo	8.8	1.8	2.89	0.16	284
mean	9.8	1.9 *	3.44	0.32 *	414

* Difference between fields and wood sites $P \leq 0.1$

Fig 1. Changes in enchytraeid densities in the shelterbelt S (data for S11 – see Table 1) and in the field (data for F_{50} – see Table 3) as a function of precipitation (the ratio of half a year sum of precipitation to the long-term average) in the years 1999–2005 in April and October.

were low in the control forest (Wo) – 88%, and the highest in the control field (FC) – 268% (in April) but there was no significant difference between plots of both study transects (S6-F, S11-F). It seems that the temporal and spatial variability of the animals' numbers is similar in both types of site irrespective of the differences in absolute values of numbers.

The range of density and biomass of enchytraeids for all study sites accounted for 1.6 to 15.3 ind. m⁻² and 55 to 956 mg f.w. (i.e. 15–308 mg d.w.m⁻²) respectively.

In 2004 the highest mean density was found in 6 yrs old shelterbelt (S6) and the lowest – in 11 yrs old (S11) and in accompanying ecotone E_r . The density and the biomass in the control field, FC (located in deforested area) were lower than in the

two other field sites adjoining woodlots (Table 1).

The values of densities found in field sites in 2004 fell within the range reported before i.e. 3.4–13.2 × 10³ m⁻² (Nowak 2004). In the wood sites data for the 11 yrs old shelterbelt (S 11–1.6 × 10³ m⁻²) fell out of the range reported before (6.9–15.3 × 10³ m⁻²). The mean individual size (Table 1) was generally lower in second study period than in the first one due to mass autumnal hatching of *Enchytraeus* sp. but is also less in fields than in wood sites. Individuals from the control field – FC – were significantly smaller (2.25 mm) than the individuals from the fields adjacent to forest strips ($P < 0.03$). Therefore, the biomass in control site was also lower (72 mg f.w. i.e. 0.2 mg d.w. m⁻²) than that noted in 1999–2000 pe-

riod in field habitats (127–394 mg f.w. i.e. 36–81 mg d.w.m⁻²).

As in the 1999–2000 studies the densities noted in each ecotone E_f were not higher than in two bordering sites – S and F₁₅. Higher density and species diversity of enchytraeids were expected in these habitats due to the neighbourhood of wood strips with rich fauna of enchytraeids. The density records basing on the means for three sampling occasions for each plot displayed the same trend (Fig. 2). Among 13 sampling occasions only three times in all study period the enchytraeid density in ecotone sites was higher than in the shelterbelt or in the field at a distance of 10–15 m from the ecotone. Similarly the high diversity (H') in ecotone plot was noted only once in both study periods.

The density of enchytraeids was different in the field plots at two distances from the shelterbelt's edge. The density was significantly ($P < 0.001$) higher at F₁₅ than in the ecotone E_f and in the middle of the field F₅₀, even higher than in any other plot (Fig. 2). The content of organic matter and phosphates concentration were in F₁₅ lower than mean values from two neighbouring sites (Bernacki unpublished) as well as C:N ratio of organic matter was higher in this plot (Kostro-Chomać 2003). High density of enchytraeids connect with specificity of this place.

In the shelterbelts S2 and S7 the density of enchytraeids slightly increased with age of vegetation i.e. from 2 to 7 years (ANOVA $P = 0.000$ $F = 4.28$). During that time the density achieved the values characteristic for soil

Table 2. Species composition and % share in the total numbers of enchytraeids in study sites in 2004. E_f – ecotone site close to shelterbelt of respective age in years; other site symbols see Table 1.

	Wo	FC	S6	E _f 6	F6	S11	E _f 11	F11
<i>Acheta bohemica</i> (Vejd.)	40				<1			1
“ <i>camerani</i> Cog.	20	20	20	4	2	5	16	
“ <i>eiseni</i> Vejd.	9	3	26	1	2	3	7	
“ sp.	10							
<i>Enchytraeus</i> sp*	–	68	33	65	82	60	25	82
<i>Henlea ventriculosa</i> d'Udek	1		23	7	1	13		1
<i>Enchytronia parva</i> Niel et Chr.	6	8		5	2	3	6	
<i>Buchholzia fallax</i> Mich	4							
<i>Fridericia bisetosa</i> (Lev.)	2		5	2	4	16	11	10
“ <i>bulboides</i> Niel et Ch.	<1		13	12	4		22	11
“ <i>gracilis</i> Büllow				2	3			
“ <i>leydygi</i> (Vejd.)				2				
“ <i>perieri</i> (Vejd.)		1						
<i>Cognetia sphagnetorum</i> (Vejd.)	7							
<i>Mesenchytraeus armatus</i> (Lev.)	1							
<i>Marionina</i> sp							3	
number of species	10	5	6	9	9	6	7	7
diversity index H'	2.26	1.35	2.42	1.85	1.20	1.77	2.53	1.46

* *Enchytraeus buchholzi* + *E. christenseni*

Table 3. Enchytraeids' density and distribution (% in upper soil layer) and the contribution (%) of *Enchytraeus sp.* in the soil taken below the exposed litter (UL) and in the neighbouring soil (NL) – for the different sites. Site symbols see Table 1 and 2; F₅₀ and F₁₅ – in-field plots at the distance 50 and 15 m from the edge of shelterbelt. Data for 12 and 18 months of experiment with the litter (dried matter of *Dactylis glomerata*) exposed on the soil surface. ($P < 0.01^{**}$, 0.02^*).

Site	Density 10^3 m^{-2}			% in 0–5 cm soil layer			% of <i>Enchytraeus sp.</i>		
	NL	UL	<i>P</i>	NL	UL	<i>P</i>	NL	UL	<i>P</i>
FC	2.0	2.2	–	5	36	**	39	53	–
12 months F ₅₀	1.0	1.1	–	20	45	–	33	66	–
F ₁₅	35.0	10.5	**	39	52	**	93	89	–
E _f	2.2	2.1	–	50	68	–	10	53	**
S11	2.2	1.8	–	36	78	**	44	82	*
18 months FC	0.8	6.7	–	40	23	–	40	88	**
F ₅₀	4.3	8.0	–	35	48	–	25	39	–
F ₁₅	22.5	23.3	–	15	67	**	77	86	–
E _f	7.2	9.7	–	21	24	–	39	38	–
S11	3.2	3.8	–	79	48	–	65	68	–

Fig 2. Mean enchytraeid densities in shelterbelts (S6 and S11), in ecotone plots (Ef) and inside the fields at two distances (F15 and F50 m) from the shelterbelts. Site symbols see Table 1 and 2.

types of these habitats (Fig. 3). This regularity was not valid for 11 yrs old shelterbelt (S11) where very low animals' density was noted in 2004.

The density of enchytraeids in fields accounted for 67% of that in shelterbelt sites. Size of individuals was significantly ($P = 0.03$) smaller in the former than in the latter. Total biomass of enchytraeids in field sites was 47% of that in shelterbelts. This comparison between woody and field areas was evaluated

based on the 14 data given in Table 1, among others, from the two transects investigated in 2000 and 2004 and the data from two control sites – field and forest.

The species richness (species number) in the period 2002–2004 ranges from 5 in the control field (FC) to 10 in the large forest (Wo) (Table 2). In 2000 the number of species along the same transect ranged between 4–12. One new forest species *Mesenchytraeus armatus* appeared in 2004 as compared with

Fig 3. Enchytraeid densities in shelterbelts (S) of different age – 2, 5, 6, 7 and 11 years after planting and in the oldest (150 yrs) woodstrip and control forest stand (Wo). Data for 2000 and 2004.

Fig. 4. Species similarity of enchytraeids (Euclidean distance, complete linkage clustering). Site symbols see Tables 1 and 2.

the composition in 2000. The species *Cognetia sphagnetorum* appeared two times – in 2004 in the forest and in 2000 – in the old shelterbelt (S150). The highest species diversity (H') was found in the forest, in one ecotone and in one shelterbelt, but in all field sites the diversity was low (Table 2). *Enchytraeus* sp was the dominant genus in studied sites (78–82% of total numbers). The individuals of this genus were not found only in the large forest (Wo) and formerly also in 150 yrs old shelterbelt

(S150) (Table 2). In both these forest habitats pine needles and leaves of the locust tree make the soil acidified (Bernacki upubl.) and that was probably the reason why this genus doesn't occur in these sites.

Basing on both lists of species (from 2000 and 2004) the similarity between species composition of enchytraeid communities was analysed (Fig. 4). Nine communities occurring in the fields and wood strips were remarkably similar one to the other. The

communities of forest site, Wo as well as of 150 yrs old shelterbelt (S150) were markedly distinct (Fig. 4).

3.2. Enchytraeids' response to experimentally increased input of plant litter

Comparison of densities and species composition of enchytraeids in soil samples taken below the exposed litter and from nearby vicinity shows time related effects. In the autumn, after one year of litter exposure, enchytraeids' densities in the soil just below the litter in sites S11, E_p, F₅₀ and FC were insignificantly higher than in nearby soil. In site F₁₅ where the animal density was high – less enchytraeids were found below the litter than nearby (Table 3). More distinct influence of introduced litter was found half a year later (spring samples) i.e. after 18 months. More enchytraeids was found in all sites in the soil below the litter than in the soil nearby. However, the difference becomes significant when site F₁₅ is excluded (because of enormous densities in the autumn) from calculations. The numbers of individuals in the soil below the litter and nearby (7 versus 3.9 ind. per sample) in combined four remaining sites (FC, F₅₀, E_p, S) appeared to be statistically significant at $P = 0.03$.

Enchytraeus sp. dominated more distinctly (79%) in the soil taken below the exposed litter than in the nearby soil sample (73%) although this difference is marginally significant ($P = 0.1$) (Table 3). In samples taken in the autumn 2004 the numbers of this taxon were significantly higher in sites S11 and E_f and also on average in four combined sites of S11, E_p, F₅₀ and FC ($P = 0.0006$). In spring 2005 the predominance of *Enchytraeus* in below-litter samples was weaker. However, it was significant in the control field FC ($P = 0.005$), marginally significant in site F₁₅ ($P = 0.09$) and again significant in the remaining combined sites (54% of the numbers in soil below the litter and 40% – in nearby soil, $P = 0.02$).

Vertical distribution of enchytraeids was markedly different in the samples below the litter and in nearby soil (Table 3). In the autumn there were more animals in the upper 5 cm soil layer (the differences were significant at $P = 0.006$ in sites FC, S11 and F₁₅ and

insignificant in sites F₅₀ and E_p, $P = 0.12$). In spring the numerical predominance of animals in the upper layer was significant in F₁₅ and in remaining sites taken together.

The observed distribution was probably caused by reason other than variability in soil moisture as soil moisture was the same below the exposed litter and nearby (88% and 93%, respectively, the differences were statistically insignificant).

4. DISCUSSION

There are no significant differences in the spatial and temporal variability of enchytraeids' density in field and shelterbelt sites. In the former studies (Nowak 2004) it has been found that the temporal fluctuations of density in fields was higher than that in shelterbelts. Present records of densities (Fig. 1) suggest the another situation. The spatial variability measured with CV% index in the present studies did not differentiate both types of sites. The reason of this is probably connected with the equally unstable conditions in shelterbelts – like in the field sites – due to rapid succession of vegetation in the latter (Bernacki 2004).

The density of enchytraeids in shelterbelts increases with the age of their vegetation to the level found in neighbouring old woody habitats (Fig. 3).

The values of the density, size and species composition of enchytraeids in control fields (sites F0 and FC – this last located in the deforested area) were low but did not differ significantly from these parameters in the fields adjacent to the shelterbelts (Table 1).

The experimental increase of litter input was expected to provoke the response of animals proportional to litter shortage in the habitat – larger in the field, smaller in woodlot. In the soil taken below the introduced litter after one year of its exposure different vertical distribution and more marked domination of *Enchytraeus* sp. were found in all sites, not only in the field plots. It is not reasonable to relate these changes to physical conditions in soil because for instance – the soil moisture below the litter was similar to that nearby. The genus *Enchytraeus* is known to prefer soils of moderate acidity (Pilipiuk 2003) and in studied sites it avoided acidified

habitats like shelterbelts with locust (S150) and pine trees (Wo). Decaying of the introduced litter slightly decreased soil pH (by 0.5 pH units – Szanser, unpublished) but despite this the density and domination of *Enchytraeus* sp. increased in the soil below the litter. The food of this genus is composed of streptomyces and microscopic fungi (Kristoufek *et al.* 1995, 2001). The increase of *Enchytraeus* sp. domination rather followed the increase of these groups of microorganisms than the changes in physical soil properties.

After 18 months of litter exposure an increase of enchytraeid densities was observed in the soil below the litter as compared to neighbouring soil. It was relatively rapid response as far as enchytraeids are considered to assimilate organic matter in litter at 5th to 10th year of its decomposition (Briones and Ineson 2002).

Species composition was similar in fields and shelterbelts and differed only in old woody habitats i.e. in the control forest stand and in 150 yrs old shelterbelt.

The results seem to support the conclusion that enchytraeids are well adapted to field conditions although these habitats are poor in organic matter because of frequent yield removal. Comparison with other animals shows that they might be the main consumers of organic matter in field habitats (Nowak 2004) but choose the matter at later (at least more than a 1.5 year old) stages of decomposition. Densities, biomass and diversity of these animals did not differ between fields and shelterbelts, being slightly smaller in the former irrespective of markedly limited input of plant remnants. The reasons might be looked for in biocoenotic interactions as in the shelterbelts the increase of the predators biomass (Kajak and Oleszczuk 2004, Kajak 2007, Olechowicz 2007) and the saprophages dependent on litter fall (Makulec 2004, Olechowicz 2004, Olechowicz 2007) was stated.

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